

Employees' Well-Being and Attitudes during Work Hours In Brunei Public Sector

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Abstract

The purpose of this study is to investigate relationship between well-being and attitudes of civil servants during working hours. A cross-sectional research was conducted ($n=405$) across ministries in Brunei from non-executive services to executive services. A validated 14-item Warwick-Edinburgh Mental Wellbeing Scale (WEMWBS) using a 5-point Likert scale was used to measure employees' well-being and working hours items were adapted from validated BAuA-Working Time Survey (BAuA-WTS) measurements. The study found positive correlations between well-being and attitudes during work hours. This study can pave a pathway for policymakers to explore possible policies and strategies to strengthen employees' well-being at work.

Keywords: *well-being, work hours, and public sector*

1. INTRODUCTION

There has been growing interest in mainstream organizational research on well-being (Warr, 1990) from a focused to a broad body of literature (De Simone, 2014), resulting existence of various definitions and conceptualizations of the term well-being, with different theoretical models, and different measurements of the term. However, definitions of mental well-being are still considered less well-researched and seen as a complex concept. Some definitions of mental well-being include those who are aware of their potential, cope very well with stress, and can make meaningful contributions to the community through working more productively and how people able to function and develop (Keyes, 2007). According to Clarke, et. al (2011), mental well-being is conceptualized as hedonic, that is subjective well-being and emotions or feelings of happiness or anxiety. They also refer to well-being as eudaimonic (positive functioning) well-being which refers to leading 'a life well lived', interacting with the world around them to meet basic psychological needs such as experiencing a sense of competence or sense of meaning and purpose.

WHO (2018) argued that socioeconomic factors such as poverty, lack of social protection, poor living standards, unhealthy working environments, chronic health conditions, alcohol and substance use disorders, and violence in conflicts, natural disasters and situations of abuse, have impact on mental well-being. Other researchers found that it is social relationships that have an impact on the mental well-being of individuals. There are also other factors that challenging employees in managing their work and family life. For example, occupational health research found causal relationship between work and mental well-being (Taris and Kompier, 2003). According to the role conflict theory, when pressures in one role are incompatible with those of another, role conflict will result. Early researchers such as Greenhaus and Beutell (1985) argued that when employees have limited resources including time, energy, and attention to spend on family life roles, or when the demands of work exceed these resources required to meet the demands of family life, work-family life conflict will occur.

The definition of working hours varies. Karhulaa et al, (2020) stated that working hours of 35 to 41 hours per week is considered average and working more than 41 hours per week is a

long working time, while Kivimaki et al (2015) argued that long working hours varied from 45 hours or more to 55 hours or more per week. Using the definition, working hours for the Brunei civil service are considered average despite previously being claimed to be among the highest in terms of long working hours in ASEAN with an average of 46.1 hours per week by the International Labour Organisation in 2022. This published working hours, however, was overgeneralized and did not specifically refer to the role, type of jobs, and sectors. The working hours in the Brunei civil service is only a total of 37.5 hours per week although no doubt some may or have ‘voluntarily’ worked beyond this number of hours. Nevertheless, it is still intriguing to examine the attitude of civil servants during the average working hours and their well-being.

2. METHODS

Participants: This study was a cross-sectional research. Questionnaires were administered via online to wide civil servants across ministries in Brunei from non-executive services (Division V) to executive services (Division I). Measurements taken include employees’ well-being and employees’ activities during work hours.

Demographic information: Personal information included gender, age, marital status and number of children. Salary scale was included for position in the civil service.

Well-being: Previous studies have used well-being measurement to identify a relationship between work hours and health (Costa 1996; Åkerstedt 1996; Kecklund et al, 2000). Similarly, this research used a validated 14-item Warwick-Edinburgh Mental Wellbeing Scale (WEMWBS) using a 5-point Likert scale from (‘None of the time’ to ‘All of the time’) to assess employees’ well-being. This measurement was considered to be robust and valid when applied in population, community, educational, occupational, and clinical settings. The scoring will provide the level of well-being according to low, moderate, and high well-being.

Work-hours and attitude: Working hours items were adapted from validated BAuA-Working Time Survey (BAuA-WTS) measurements. Items include whether they usually work within the fixed working hours; take time for resting, have meal breaks, and perform personal or family duties during the fixed working hours.

All the above measurements were conducted in English. Data were analyzed using SPSS Statistic 27 for Windows. For this preliminary study, descriptive analysis and bivariate correlations were conducted to identify relationships between variables.-

3. RESULTS

Table 1 shows that of the total 405 participants, 26.9% were male and 73.1% were females with the average of 0.73 and 33.1% aged between 29 to 39 years old and 43% aged between 40 to 50 years old with mean of 2.78. Majority of the respondents were married that is 78% and only 18.5% were still single. The salary scale showed 43.5% of the respondents were holding Division II. This variable placed respondent’s position as middle management officers in their organization. Majority of the respondents also have at least 1 child and 43% have 3 or more children. Inclusion of these variables was considered due to the interest in identifying level of well-being and employees’ attitudes towards the working hours. The table of exhibits age as having the highest mean while number of children has the highest standard deviation.

Table 1: Descriptive frequencies, mean and standard deviation of respondents' variables

Variables	N	%	Mean	SD
GENDER				
Male	109	26.9	.73	.444
Female	296	73.1		
AGE				
28 and below	17	4.2	2.78	.807
29 - 39	134	33.1		
40 - 50	174	43.0		
51 and above	80	19.8		
MARITAL STATUS				
Single	75	18.5	1.85	.444
Married	316	78.0		
Divorce/Separated	14	3.5		
SALARY SCALE				
Division I	74	18.3	2.41	1.07
Division II	176	43.5		
Division III	89	22.0		
Division IV	45	11.1		
Division V	21	5.2		
NO OF CHILDREN				
None	108	26.7	2.16	.819
1 – 2	123	30.4		
3 and above	174	43.0		

As shown in Table 2 below, only 3.21% of the respondents have a high level of well-being, while 45.43% have a moderate level of well-being, and 51.36% have low well-being. Between genders, more females than males were found to have low well-being. That is 77.9% of females had low well-being and 22.1% of males had low well-being.

Table 2: Frequencies of level of well-being and by gender

Wellbeing	Male	Female	Total	%
High	7	6	13	3.21
Low	46	162	208	51.36
Moderate	56	128	184	45.43
Total	109	296	405	100.00

Cross-tabulation was also conducted to analyses the relationship between multiple variables in this case between levels of well-being and number of children, well-being and resting time, and well-being and personal duty. Table 3 below shows 46.2% respondents have all the time to have meal breaks, have high level of well-being. Those 68.7% of respondents who do not, rarely and sometimes have meal breaks have low well-being.

Table 3: Cross-tabulation between level of well-being and having meal breaks during work hours

		None of the time	Rarely	Some of the time	Often	All of the time	Total
Level of Well-being	High	7.7%	30.8%	15.4%	0%	46.2%	100.0%
	Low	2.4%	21.6%	44.7%	25.0%	6.3%	100.0%
	Moderate	3.3%	14.7%	26.6%	38.0%	17.4%	100.0%
Total		3.0%	18.8%	35.6%	30.1%	12.6%	100.0%

Cross-tabulation between the level of well-being and taking rest time during work hours was also computed. Table 4 below exhibits 69.3% of the respondents who sometimes, often and all the time take resting time, have a high level of well-being, and only 30.8% who do not take rest time or rarely have rest time have a high level of well-being. While 91.4% of respondents have no rest time, rarely and only sometimes take rest time, found to have low well-being.

Table 4: Cross-tabulation between the level of well-being and taking rest time during work hours

		None of the time	Rarely	Some of the time	Often	All of the time	Total
Level of Well-being	High	23.1%	7.7%	30.8%	30.8%	7.7%	100.0%
	Low	8.2%	38.5%	44.7%	7.2%	1.4%	100.0%
	Moderate	6.0%	27.7%	37.5%	20.7%	8.2%	100.0%
Total		7.7%	32.6%	41.0%	14.1%	4.7%	100.0%

Another cross-tabulation was conducted between the level of well-being and performing personal duty including school run during work hours. Table 5 below shows that 65.8% of the respondents who have low well-being stated that they sometimes, often, and all of the time perform personal duties including school runs as compared to 53.9% of those who have high mental well-being are either rarely or none of the time perform personal duty during working hours.

Table 5: Cross-tabulation between the level of well-being and perform personal duty including school run during work hours

		None of the time	Rarely	Some of the time	Often	All of the time	Total
Level of Well-being	High	23.1%	30.8%	7.7%	7.7%	30.8%	100.0%
	Low	15.9%	18.3%	22.1%	24.5%	19.2%	100.0%
	Moderate	17.4%	23.9%	19.0%	18.5%	21.2%	100.0%
Total		16.8%	21.2%	20.2%	21.2%	20.5%	100.0%

Table 6 below depicts 80.6% of respondents who sometimes, often and all of the time performed personal duties including doing school runs stated that they do not have time to rest, when cross-tabulation between the resting time and perform personal duty including school run during work hours were computed.

Table 6: Cross-tabulation between the resting time and perform personal duty including school run during work hours

		None of the time	Rarely	Some of the time	Often	All of the time	Total
Resting time	None of the time	12.9%	6.5%	16.1%	25.8%	38.7%	100.0%
	Rarely	18.2%	22.7%	15.2%	22.0%	22.0%	100.0%
	Some of the time	15.1%	20.5%	30.1%	18.7%	15.7%	100.0%
	Often	14.0%	28.1%	10.5%	26.3%	21.1%	100.0%
	All of the time	36.8%	21.1%	5.3%	15.8%	21.1%	100.0%
Total		16.8%	21.2%	20.2%	21.2%	20.5%	100.0%

Table 7 below presents the mean values, standard deviation and correlation coefficients among the studied variables. Having meal break and resting time are found to be significantly correlated to work hours when respondents were asked “Are your working hours usually between 7.45 am and 4.30 pm?” Respondents indicated that they have meal break in between work hours ($p < 0.01$), and have resting time during working hours ($p < 0.01$). Well-being was also found to be significantly correlated to work hours ($p < 0.05$). This table also shows a positive relationship between meal breaks and resting time ($p < 0.01$) and well-being ($p < 0.01$). Resting time, however have a negative relationship with performing personal duty ($p > 0.05$), but have a positive relationship with well-being ($p < 0.01$). Interestingly, personal duty including doing school runs did not show a significant relationship with work hours, meal breaks, and well-being.

Table 7: Inter-correlations between employees’ background, level of well-being, and work attitude

	Variable	M	SD	1	2	3	4	5
1	Usual work hours	3.81	1.152	-				
2	Meal break	3.31	1.010	0.001**	-			
3	Resting time	2.76	0.950	0.002**	0.000**	-		
4	Personal duty	3.07	1.384	-0.869	0.186	-0.46*	-	
5	Wellbeing level	2.42	0.556	0.032*	0.001**	0.000**	0.621	-

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

* . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

DISCUSSION

This study reveals well-being has a positive relationship with usual work hours and have attitude of having meal breaks and having resting time during working hours. This is anticipated and supports the hedonic approach which defines well-being in terms of life satisfaction. Performing personal duties such as doing school runs was found to have a significant negative relationship with resting time. This indicates that those who do school runs do not have time to rest. As a result, employees tend to take rest and have meal breaks in between working hours. These findings support the notion of work-family conflict literature which has been of increasing particular interest due to family responsibilities. In this present study where the majority of the participants have at least one child, and assuming their children were of schooling age, parents were obliged to do school runs during working hours. Many previous studies found problems in balancing work–family interface among female employees because they are primarily responsible for the home and children, and therefore they have to balance the demands arising from family and work roles (Kinnunen, et. al, 2003). This supports the reasons for more female employees to have low well-being in this present study.

Kinnunen et.al (20023) further highlighted several research findings that employees who reported having more work–family conflict tends to experience clinically significant mental health problems. However, this present study showed no relationship between employees' mental well-being and performing personal duties. It could be due to the

implication of positive reappraisal strategy in dealing with stressors. In this study, the mutual arrangement of flexible working hours in the respective organisation and also employers allowing employees to have resting time and having meals during work hours. Hence this finding supports previous study that predictors of positive well-being also include coping (Smith, 2003) which is the positive reappraisal that enables individuals to adapt successfully to stressful life events (Karademas, 2007). While Kundi et. al (1995) found a significant correlation between satisfaction with work hours and subjective health. They found the possibility of taking breaks over work hours as a potential determinant of well-being. It is also found that high mental well-being among the employees in the public sector which could be as a result of the lower working hours, which is contrary to earlier studies such as Bannai and Tamakoshi (2014) that found depressive state, anxiety, sleep condition, and coronary heart disease are associated with long working hours.

5. CONCLUSION

These findings have important implications for workplace policy and the prevention of mental illness among civil servants. Strengthening regulation of working hours and improving time management skills among working-age people in workplaces, are conducive to their well-being status. Future studies should adopt a longitudinal methodology to identify the causal relationships between usual/average working hours and psychological outcomes, include a more representative sample with higher generalizability, and work hours arrangement in more detail to determine which one can best enhance workers' mental well-being. This study thus is vital to provide policymakers with more understanding of employees' well-being in the workplace and perhaps the outcome of the research could pave a pathway to explore possible policies and strategies for existing concerns.

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